

AN OVERVIEW ON KUSHTHA VYADHI

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ABSTRACT

The skin is the largest organ of the body, it acts as a mirror, reflecting internal health conditions. Acharya Sushruta described the formation of Twacha in the developing foetus. He says that after fertilization of ovum Twacha develops just like cream on the surface of the boiled milk. Acharya Vagbhata also followed the same. Twacha is one among the Matruja Bhava. According to Vagbhata, Twacha formation in the foetus will be completed in the sixth month. Vagbhata described the formation of Twacha due to Paka of Rakta Dhatu by its Dhatwagni in the foetus. After Paka, it dries up to form Twacha. The health of skin is influenced by variety of factors, including hygiene, nutrition, age, immunity, psychological state etc. in modern society the prevalence of fast food&sleep patterns contributed to emergence of “viruddha ahar janya vyadhi” Kushtha in ayurvedic literature consist of acne,

eczema, melanoma, blisters etc. Kushta are classified broadly into 2 categories Maha kushtha & Kshudra kushtha i. e. Major skin diseases and minor skin diseases respectively.

KEYWORDS: Maha kushtha, kshudra kushtha, Twacha formation.

INTRODUCTION

The word kushtha is derived from the “Kus Nishkarshane” by adding suffix “TKA” to it.^[1]
The meaning of kush is to extract, pull or draw out.

Definition

कुष्णाति इति कुष्ठम् (Ma. Ni.)

According to charaka Samhita.

1. Vata: Raukshya, Sosha, Toda, Shula, Ayama, Harsha, Samkochana, Syava-Arunatva
2. Pitta: Daha, Raga, Paka, Kleda Angapatana, visragandha.
3. Kapha: Shvaitya, Shaithya, Kandu, Gaurav, Sneha kleda.

CHIKITSA

वातोत्तरेषु सर्पिर्वमनं श्लेष्मोत्तरेषु कुष्ठेषु ।

पित्तोत्तरेषु मोक्षो रक्तस्य विरेचनं चाग्रे ॥⁸

(च. चि. 7/39)

In vata dosha dominant kushta ghritpan is suggested, In pitta dosha dominant kushta Raktamokshan & Virechan chikitsa is suggested & in kapha dosha Pradhan kushta vaman chikitsa is suggested in charak chikitsa sthan.

Nidan parivarjan

Bahya parimarjan chikitsa (Lepa)

Antaha parimarjana chikitsa (Aushad sevan)

Kushtanashaka Yoga:

Churna: Mustadi churna, kushtadi churna, Triphaladi churna

Kwatha: Patoladi kwatha

Lepa: Sidhmadi Lepa, Kushtadi Lepa

Ghrita: Mahakhadir ghrita, Mahatikta ghrita

Taila: Kushtadi taila

Asava: Madyasava

Arishta: Kanakbindu arishta, Khadirarishta

DISCUSSION

Kushtha is recognized as one of most chronic disorder.

Kushtha is classified as one of Ashtamahagadas by ancient ayurvedic scholars. Dermatological disorders described in modern medicines may be compared with the kushta roga.^[9]

Genetic factors, environmental factors, dietic factors, and immunological factors play important role in the pathogenesis of kushta roga including psoriasis.

In ayurveda holistic approach is suggested which includes herbal remedies, dietary management, Yoga, Pranayam which aims to address both physical & psychological aspects

of these conditions. several studies suggests strong relation between the psychological stress & psoriasis.

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda is a science of life. the principle of ayurveda is “Swasthasya swasthya raskshanam” which means to keep safe health of healthy person & prevention of future diseases.^[10]

In ayurveda kushtha is formed due to various factors.

By following proper Dinacharya (daily regiment) & Rutucharya (seasonal regiment) and keeping mind healthy by yoga, pranayama kushta vyadhi can be controlled & healthy skin can be achieved.

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